

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ARTISTIC AND JOURNALISTIC DISCOURSE IN CREATIVITY

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Abstract. This article reflects on the concept of speech culture and its importance in radio journalism. Today's radio journalistic speech should be clear and strictly organized, understandable to all. Especially the journalist should have a deep grasp of thought and word etiquette. Using words in their place increases the effectiveness of the word, serves to quickly advance the essence of the event.

Keywords: language, speech, speech etiquette, oratory, literary language.

ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО И ПУБЛИКАТИЧЕСКОГО ДИСКУРСА В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ

Аннотация. В статье размышляется о понятии культуры речи и ее значении в радиожурналистике. Сегодняшняя радиожурналистская речь должна быть четкой и строго организованной, понятной всем. Особенно журналист должен глубоко понимать мысль и словесный этикет. Использование слов вместо них повышает эффективность слова, способствует быстрому раскрытию сути события.

Ключевые слова: язык, речь, речевой этикет, ораторское искусство, литературный язык.

In our country, which is rapidly moving on the path of innovative development today, the upbringing of a harmonious generation, the cultivation of enlightened and highly spiritual citizens is one of the priorities of the policy of our state.

The concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, as defined by our country, shows its positive result today. In our country, a person, a person, Society, a state are being renewed, all social process Education and culture, spirituality are being formed in a unique way.

Language and speech are related phenomena. Language is material material for speech, on the basis of this material speech is formed. Everything in the language will be common to the language community. The language contains spiritual and material material, the figurative spiritual material of the word in the memory of people, the forms of the word used in the process of creating speech, morphemes, sounds are material material. While the fact that language is a spiritual phenomenon is its preservation in the mind, its material phenomena are determined through the means of language in it.

Speech is the process of using a unique weapon, the so-called Language, performing extremely important tasks, the manifestation of the possibilities of language units in relation to phenomena such as being, thinking, consciousness and situation. Speech is a language in motion,

appearing in the process of the movement of speech members and is formed from word forms, vocabulary and sentences. The culture of speech, the concept of striving for cultural speaking is a phenomenon that has existed in all folk languages since time immemorial. This concept is considered a concept that is associated with certain linguistic norms, ethical and aesthetic requirements.

While functional speech styles, scientific, formal, colloquial styles report one or another manifestations of life, the activities of the Professional of the people engaged in it, the style of artistic speech is characterized by a mixture of all aspects of life and existing speech styles. The artistic style not only gives a message, information about the event, but also gives an aesthetic effect to the reader, the listener, the main function of which is figurativeness. And through figurativeness, speech reveals the character, characteristics of the owner. This style uses all the linguistic elements present in the general language based on the literary norm, and sometimes there are also cases of deviations from the literary norm, in which the writer, author can deviate to reveal character traits. In this style, the scale of the artistic perception of reality, the method of creativity, poetic skills of each writer differ from each other in a way that is in accordance with the genre nature of artistic speech. Accordingly, the artistic style of speech is an extremely inclusive and rich speech vision with relatively wide possibilities.

The phenomenon and scientific problem, which is now referred to by the term speech culture, has a much wider content. The culture of speech is not only an effort to consciously and purposefully humiliate the literary language, but also an activist who serves to raise the general culture of the nation, to educate people about the taste of a certain language.

The term speech culture is used in modern linguistic interpretation as the name of three different phenomena.

These are:

- 1) the name of cultural speech, that is, a speech phenomenon;
- 2) the name of the scientific problem associated with the concept of cultural speech and referred to as speech culture;
- 3) the name of the field specially engaged in the study of the problem of speech culture, the Department of linguistic science.

Each of the three events cited should not be confused with each other.

In understanding and describing the concept of speech culture, the following views are prominent in linguistics:

1. Speech culture is one of the peculiarities of the development of the literary language (Prague linguistic school).
2. Speech culture (language culture) is an activity that consists in helping to form and smooth literary language norms, that is, conscious intervention in language development (Prague linguistic school)
3. Speech culture is the skill of being able to make language clear, expressive. (A. Gurevich).
4. The culture of speech consists in the mutual complete and thoughtful thinking of people, a thorough mastery of all the possibilities and means of language, (B.N.Golovin).
5. The culture of speech is not only the correct speech, but also the colloquial cheapness.

(G.O. Vinokur)

6. Speech culture is the art of being able to speak and write purposefully using language tools appropriately. (A.N.Efimov).

7. The culture of speech is primarily a culture of thinking. (D. E. Rosenthal).

8. Speech, which is also distinguished by its national identity, is cultural speech. (M. Afganova).

From the definitions it is known that the culture of speech is the attitude towards the use of language as a weapon of communication – intervention. The higher the attitude of radio journalists to the use of this unique weapon, the higher the culture of speech.

In the following years, special attention is paid to the study and research of the individual characteristics of journalistic speech.

The study of his skills in the choice and application of words in the field of journalism is of particular importance in the development of our linguistics. Because it is through this aspect that the individual style of the journalist is evident. Therefore, in our linguistics, aspects such as the originality of a journalist's speech, his use of language tools are rising to the level of the main topic.

The methodological analysis of the speech of a Radio journalist consists in determining the skill of a journalist in the use of the means of artistic representation of the language, as well as the use of the language in general, and, through this, its place in the development of the Uzbek language.

The study of the methodology of the speech of a Radio journalist assumes the performance of the following tasks:

- Study of the peculiarities of radio journalism among journalistic genres;
- Scientific-critical assessment of the state of study of journalism in Uzbek linguistics;
- Analysis of phonetic properties of radio journalism;
- Study of linguistic principles of radio journalism;
- Studying the morphemic properties of radio journalism and analyzing it;

The significance of the media's information dissemination, cultural-spiritual, unifying, organizational, educational, ideological tasks is expanding in the development of the population from various events, raising the culture of the population, enriching its spirituality, and correctly shaping its worldview.

It can be seen from these points that the culture of speech is the grammatical correctness of speech. It must also be methodically correct, that is, brevity, accuracy and simplicity must be its measure. In the broadest sense, however, speech culture expresses oratory impressiveness, creative brilliance, sharpness and figurativeness. At this point, a true journalist achieves his oratory skills as a result of his natural ability, as well as his tireless work on his language, speech. In some people, oratory is an art that is achieved due to personal abilities and activities. In eloquence, we can see that ability and skill are closely related.

So today's radio journalistic speech should be clear and concise, strictly organized, understandable to all. Especially the journalist should have a deep grasp of thought and word etiquette. Using words in their place increases the effectiveness of the word, serves to quickly advance the essence of the event. As Rahimboy Jumaniozov explained, "journalism is a periodic

barometer of society. Whether it is a news that sets the stage for progress or, on the contrary, the first information about something contrary to it, we will receive at speed, for which the word journalist and himself must be sharp, the mention of his opinion must be thoughtful.

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